

Parameters and their use in monitoring blood flow and evaluating waste clearance at home

Xiaoqiu Huang
Department of Computer Science
Iowa State University
Ames, Iowa 50011, USA

Corresponding Author:
Xiaoqiu Huang
Email address: xqhuang@iastate.edu

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Abstract

Blood flow patterns in the body change in response to activity. The ability to monitor changes in blood flow pattern at home during the day is useful in optimizing neurovascular benefits via activity. Previous studies have established direct relationships between blood flow and temperature in peripheral tissues and in the brain. In this study, I measured palm and forehead temperature to understand how blood flow patterns change in response to qigong and other activities. I found that the relaxation response elicited by qigong leads to an increase in hand blood flow but a decrease in brain blood flow slightly below resting levels. This finding is in disagreement with the current understanding that the relaxation response increases blood flow to the brain above resting levels. I describe the unexpected effect of increased blood flow on the health of my fingers over the years. This study also presents a case to illustrate that passing gas out of the body is an important part of waste clearance. Thus I propose that the number of times the body passes gas during the day be used as a measure of the effectiveness of diet and behavior in waste clearance.

Introduction

I had an unhealthy diet early in my life, and found it hard to do exercise such as running. I started my qigong practice on New Year's Day in 1983 and have practiced it every morning since. I noticed that the qigong practice helped my body pass gas more frequently. Over time, I found that eating foods rich in vitamin C, drinking more water, and cutting down on sugar, rice, bread and beans were beneficial to my body. Both qigong and meditation induce the relaxation response (Benson and Klipper 1975), the opposite of the stress response. Qigong is an active form with gentle and relaxed physical movements, while meditation is a still form with relaxed mental activities. Meditation induces low oxygen consumption (Benson and Klipper 1975), but increases blood flow to the prefrontal cortex (Newberg et al. 2003). One of the benefits I found from my qigong practice is that after I got headache from stress at work, a short qigong practice would make my headache disappear. Since stress is often accompanied with an increase in blood flow to the brain (Bryan 1990), does qigong induce a decrease in blood flow to the brain below or towards resting levels?

Blood flow is important in providing nutrients and oxygen to muscles and organs, in cleaning neurons and blood, and in removing toxins, wastes and excess nutrients from the body. Blood flow measurement requires expensive equipment that is not available to ordinary households. However, the literature on blood flow supports my proposal that changes in blood flow to the hands and forehead are reflected by changes in their temperature, as explained below. First, direct relationships between temperature and blood flow are established in peripheral tissues (Kiyatkin 2010). For example, the simultaneous measurement of forearm and hand blood flow, and palm temperature during exercise showed that the temperature change reflected the blood flow changes (Kojima et al. 1985). Palm temperature reflects the palm blood flow (Crandall et al. 2005). During qigong, the temperature on the palm is increased during emission of qi (Tokuo et al. 1988). However, qi is an unverified concept (Lee et al. 2008). These studies along with my own experiences with qigong (see Results) suggest that during qigong, an increase in palm temperature reflects the hand blood flow increases. Second, across multiple cortical areas in the brain, average capillary blood flow is largely increased during rapid eye movement (REM) sleep (Tsai et al. 2021). During non-REM sleep, slow oscillatory neuronal activity leads to oscillations in blood volume, drawing cerebrospinal fluid into and out of the brain (Fultz et al. 2019). Transitions to wakefulness or REM sleep are accompanied by an increase in brain temperature, while transitions to non-REM sleep are accompanied by a decrease in brain

temperature (Harding et al. 2019). The above studies suggest direct relationships between temperature and blood flow in the brain.

A first goal of this study was to demonstrate the ability to monitor changes in blood flow pattern during the day at home. I measured palm and forehead temperature to understand how blood flow patterns change in response to qigong and other activities. I found that the relaxation response elicited by qigong leads to an increase in hand blood flow but a decrease in brain blood flow slightly below resting levels. A second goal was to propose that the number of times the body passes gas during the day be used as a measure of the effectiveness of diet and behavior in waste clearance. I present a case to illustrate that passing gas out of the body is an important part of waste clearance. A third goal was to illustrate the importance of maintaining optimal levels of blood flow in the body to keep neurons and nerves healthy over the long term. I describe the unexpected effect of the increased hand blood flow elicited by my qigong practice on the health of my fingers over the years.

Methods

Parameters in measuring changes in blood flow

All measurements in this study were performed with a household temperature scanner and a household blood pressure monitor. No medications or supplements were used in this study. No experiments or methods that require an approval from the authorities were used in this study. I taught myself a style of qigong called Soaring Crane and have practiced my own variant of this style over the years.

Most of the measurements performed in this study were on forehead and palm temperature. Forehead temperature and palm temperature are important for the health of the neurons in the forehead and the nerves in the hands, because sweat glands with the highest density have been formed on the palms of the hands and on the forehead, as well as on the soles of the feet, to cool them. Forehead temperature and palm temperature are also controlled by the regulation of blood flow in the body.

Forehead temperature and palm temperature vary with their ambient temperature, and so do brain blood flow and hand blood flow. These parameters also vary by the time of day. To minimize the impacts of fluctuations in the ambient temperature and the time of day, only changes in forehead and palm temperature that happened in the same environment

over a short period of time were considered in this study. To determine if a change in palm (or forehead) temperature during an activity could be attributed to a change in palm (or brain) blood flow in response to the activity, a resting state and a resting palm (or forehead) temperature range were introduced. I was in a resting state when I wore a comfortable level of clothing at home, and had not experienced discomfort in my body or participated in any activity of moderate intensity or higher (such as exercise, qigong, shopping, meeting, eating, bowel movement) within the past 30 minutes. My healthy resting palm (or forehead) temperature range for the day was determined by taking my palm (or forehead) temperature measurements in the resting state at various times during the day from 6 July to 10 August 2023. If a change in palm or forehead temperature is outside its resting temperature range during an activity, called a major change, then this change is likely to be associated with the activity; if not for the activity, the change would unlikely be outside the range. Major changes in palm and forehead temperature can occur during activity and stress (see Results).

The literature on blood flow during activity is useful in checking if a major change in palm or forehead temperature during an activity reflects a change in blood flow during the activity. Some studies have found blood flow patterns during several types of stress and activity, and other studies have established direct relationships between blood flow and temperature. Our common experiences can confirm some associations between stress and palm (or forehead) temperature. First, consider cold stress. Blood flow to the hands and brain is reduced upon exposure to cold (Cheung 2015; Gibbons 2021). The hands and the forehead also feel cold in a cold environment. The cold hands and forehead reflect decreases in blood flow to them. Second, consider another common stress called the fight or flight response. This type of stress results in increased brain blood flow in several regions, including temporal and prefrontal cortex (Wang et al. 2005; Elbau et al. 2018); it is well known that the stress leads to decreased hand blood flow. During the fight or flight response, the forehead feels hot due to increased blood flow to the brain, but the hands feel cold or clammy due to decreased blood flow to the hands. Third, consider heat stress. Heat stress can greatly increase skin blood flow (Chaseling et al. 2020), and skeletal muscle blood flow (Pearson et al. 2011). During heat stress, blood flow to splanchnic organs (stomach, spleen, liver, and intestine) is progressively decreased (Kregel et al. 1988); and intracranial blood flow is reduced, while extracranial blood flow is increased (Ogoh et al. 2013). Fourth, consider exercise. During treadmill exercise, palm temperature drops to a plateau phase, reflecting a decrease in hand blood flow (Kojima et al. 1985). During

high-intensity dynamic exercise, the mechanism underlying the plateau or relative decrease in cerebral blood flow appears to be partly due to thermoregulation (Sato 2011). Finally, consider the activity of eating. After eating a meal, blood flow to the small intestine is dramatically increased; whereas blood flow to the brain can be reduced (Ishizeki et al. 2019).

My palm temperature was taken on the palm of my left hand with a SmartGlow EX-ERGEN TemporalScanner by placing the probe on the center of the palm touching the skin and sweeping it across the palm while holding the button for 10 seconds. My forehead temperature was taken similarly. When I needed to monitor my palm and forehead temperature for an extended period of time such as a hour, I sat down on a chair over the period, alternating between taking temperature measurements and making gentle arm movements. I also counted the number of times my body passed gas during the day for many days in summer 2023. I produced eight files of measurements in plain text format along with a README file and made them available in Supplementary Information. The mean and standard deviation of a set of measurements, as well as a 95% bootstrap confidence interval for the mean calculated with 1,000 bootstrap replicates, were computed in the R software environment.

In the morning, I put on a proper level of clothing to prevent my body from exposure to cold or heat stress by making sure that my palm and forehead temperature readings were at the low ends of their healthy resting ranges ($97.0^{\circ}/96.5^{\circ}$ at 7:01 am). (At the end of each sentence on an action is a pair of my actual palm and forehead temperature readings in the form of Palm/Forehead along with the time when they were taken at the end of the action.) Then I stretched my arms and shoulders, put my hands on a mat insulating them from the cold floor, performed 20 push-ups, and stretched my arms and shoulders again ($96.5^{\circ}/96.2^{\circ}$ at 7:10 am). Next I sat on a mat, stretched my legs, performed 30 sit-ups, and stretched my legs again ($97.0^{\circ}/95.9^{\circ}$ at 7:22 am). Finally, I performed my morning qigong routine with my mind relaxed, directing my body to make gentle movements, and thinking of the palms of my hands and the soles of my feet; my breathing was so light that it did not get any attention from my mind ($97.5^{\circ}/96.1^{\circ}$ at 7:59 am). Afterwards, I sat on a chair and alternated between taking temperature measurements and thinking of my stomach and of the palms of my hands ($97.6^{\circ}/96.6^{\circ}$ at 8:14 am). Note that the given temperature measurements show that my forehead temperature was below its resting range at the end of the 37-minute qigong practice and rose within the range at rest in 15 minutes.

Parameter in evaluating waste clearance

The parameter I used in evaluating waste clearance from my body was to measure the number of times I passed gas during the day. Here are some of the justifications from our common experiences for why this parameter can be effective in evaluating waste clearance from the body. First, having an upset stomach leads to excess gas from the body, which allows unneutralized toxic substances to be removed from the body in the form of gas. Second, consuming excess essential nutrients is known to cause excess gas from the body, which prevents these nutrients from remaining in the colon and getting back into the blood again. Third, neuronal toxins and wastes that cannot be broken down by the liver can be removed from the body in the form of gas, which prevents these harmful substances from remaining in the colon and getting back into the blood again. Fourth, the ability to pass gas depends on diet and a proper community of microorganisms in the intestines. Certain food sources of vitamin C (such as apples, broccoli, Brussels sprouts, cauliflower and cabbage) are beneficial to the liver and most likely to cause gas. Removing neuronal toxins and wastes in the form of gas from the body is a mechanism by which gut microorganisms contribute to brain health.

In my own experiences, stress prevents my body from passing gas; my body holds and delays passing gas until I am relaxed; my qigong practice has helped my body with passing gas. During summer 2023, I made every attempt to have my body exposed to sunlight for 15 minutes a day, which allowed me to get a good night's sleep and to pass gas much more frequently than before (see Results). This observation links vitamin D to good sleep (known to give the brain a good clean) and passing more gas (considered as removing more neuronal wastes from the body in this study). Vitamin D deficiency is linked with sleep disorders and poor sleep quality (Abboud 2022), with cognitive decline (Shea et al. 2023), with liver disease (Keane et al. 2018), and with colon cancer (Klampfer 2014).

Results

Palm temperature and blood flow to the hands

My healthy resting palm temperature range during the day was $97.0^{\circ} - 98.4^{\circ}F$, with the lowest levels in the early morning, based on measurements taken from 6 July to 10 August 2023. For example, on 9 August 2023, my resting palm temperature was $97.0^{\circ}F$ at 7:01 am, and after stretching my shoulders and doing push-ups, my palm temperature was $96.2^{\circ}F$

at 7:12 am; my resting palm temperature was $97.7^{\circ}F$ at 10:59 am, and after lunch with salmon sprayed with juice from fresh lemon, my palm temperature was $96.6^{\circ} - 96.8^{\circ}F$ at 1:58–2:02 pm. The lower palm temperature reflected reduced blood flow to the hands, which happened along with increased blood flow to another part of the body such as the chest/shoulder muscles during the push-ups (Rowell 1986) or the splanchnic organs after the meal (Koffert et al. 2017). As another example, on four occasions, my palm temperature was $96.3^{\circ} - 96.8^{\circ}F$ after breakfast or morning bowel movement. Finally, an active qigong practice and then a period of standing meditation can increase my palm temperature by $0.7^{\circ}F$ within 30 minutes, which reflected increased blood flow to the hands elicited by qigong.

On a cool morning at home, my palm temperature was $97.0^{\circ}F$ after waking up and dropped to $96.2^{\circ}F$ after getting up and before doing qigong; the drop in my palm temperature probably reflected reduced blood flow to the hands in response to exposure to cold (Cheung 2015).

Forehead temperature and blood flow to the frontal lobe

My healthy resting forehead temperature range during the day was $96.5^{\circ} - 97.5^{\circ}F$, with the lowest levels in the early morning, based on measurements taken from 6 July to 10 August 2023. Blood flow to the frontal lobe can be reduced immediately after exercise and qigong. First I report one of my recent experiences with exercise. On the warm morning of 23 July 2023, I came home from moderate-intensity biking at 10:05 am and took 31 measurements of my forehead and palm temperature from 10:13 to 11:13 am, while keeping blood flow to the hands and feet activated by performing some qigong movements. These forehead temperature measurements had a mean temperature of $95.80^{\circ}F$, with a 95% confidence interval of ($95.7^{\circ}F, 95.9^{\circ}F$). The mean forehead temperature was at least $0.6^{\circ}F$ below the resting forehead temperature range. On the other hand, the palm temperature measurements had a mean of $97.7^{\circ}F$, with a 95% confidence interval of ($97.6^{\circ}F, 97.7^{\circ}F$), so the mean palm temperature was in the resting palm temperature range.

Next I present one of my recent experiences with qigong. On 25 July 2023, I finished a qigong practice at 7:13 am, and took 16 measurements of my forehead and palm temperature from 7:13 to 7:43 am. Each of the forehead temperature measurements was below the resting forehead temperature range, while each of the palm temperature measurements was inside the resting palm temperature range. These forehead temperature measurements

had a mean temperature of $96.17^{\circ}F$, with a 95% confidence interval of $(96.1^{\circ}F, 96.2^{\circ}F)$. The mean forehead temperature was $0.3^{\circ}F$ below the resting forehead temperature range, indicating a reduction in blood flow to the frontal lobe.

Palm and forehead temperature after qigong and waking up

I took and recorded my palm and forehead temperature after my morning qigong practice on 123 days from December 2020 to July 2021. My forehead temperature measurements had a mean temperature of $96.35^{\circ}F$, with a 95% confidence interval of $(96.3^{\circ}F, 96.4^{\circ}F)$. The right limit of the confidence interval was $0.1^{\circ}F$ below the resting forehead temperature range, indicating a decrease in blood flow to the frontal lobe below resting levels. My palm temperature measurements had a mean of $97.46^{\circ}F$, with a 95% confidence interval of $(97.4^{\circ}F, 97.5^{\circ}F)$. After qigong, the mean palm temperature was $1.11^{\circ}F$ above the mean forehead temperature, a sign of the relaxation response. For comparison, I took my resting palm and forehead temperature after waking up in the morning on 24 days from 14 July to 10 August: my forehead (mean = $96.72^{\circ}F$, 95% confidence interval = $(96.65^{\circ}F, 96.79^{\circ}F)$), and my palm (mean = $97.37^{\circ}F$, 95% confidence interval = $(97.27^{\circ}F, 97.45^{\circ}F)$). After waking up, the mean resting palm temperature was $0.65^{\circ}F$ above the mean resting forehead temperature, a mark of the resting response.

Incident of low palm and forehead temperature

I experienced an incident of low resting palm and forehead temperature on 7 July 2023 after eating foods high in potassium but low in calcium for four days in a row. I had a poor night's sleep and woke up one hour earlier than usual on that day, with a mean systolic blood pressure of 130.9 mmHg from eight measurements taken from 5:35 to 6:21 am. For comparison, my systolic blood pressure measurements taken each day over 11-23 July was all under 120 mmHg. In the morning of that day, I took 13 measurements of my palm and forehead temperature from 5:35 am to 7:04 am. These palm and forehead temperature readings were all below the resting palm and forehead temperature ranges, respectively: my palm (mean = $96.3^{\circ}F$, 95% confidence interval = $(96.1^{\circ}F, 96.5^{\circ}F)$), and my forehead (mean = $96.2^{\circ}F$, 95% confidence interval = $(96.1^{\circ}F, 96.3^{\circ}F)$). During the day, I was full of energy, but I had multiple episodes of liver discomfort and passed gas 62 times in total; each episode started with a little discomfort in my liver, followed by my passing gas one or more times, and ended with the discomfort going away. I did not have other digestive

problems such as constipation or diarrhea. To determine the probability of passing gas at least 62 times in a day, I recorded the number of times I passed gas on each day from 7 July to 10 August (except for 26 July), and obtained a mean of 33.8 and a standard deviation of 10.0 from these 34 measurements, and calculated the probability $P(X > 61) = 0.0033$. I noticed that I passed gas more frequently during this period than before; for example, over 15-30 June 2023, I passed gas 13 to 26 times a day (mean = 21).

Prior to this incident, my body had similar reactions after I drank bottled water with added minerals for a few days. Because I started to feel discomfort in my liver on the previous day (6 July), I decided to take blood pressure and temperature measurements and counted the number of times I passed gas for this incident.

The low temperature on my low palm and forehead at rest reflected reduced blood flow to my hands and frontal lobe, leading to increased blood flow to my other organs. My liver discomfort and passing gas suggested that my splanchnic organs were the ones that received increased blood flow. An explanation for my experience is that my liver dumped toxins and excess nutrients (likely including potassium) into my intestines and signaled the inability to perform its function. The function of the body in passing gas depends on the bacteria and foods in the intestines. Passing gas many times will remove some toxins and excess nutrients from the body, instead of allowing them to stay in the colon for many hours and to get back into the blood again. The bacteria in the intestines affect the health of the brain and other organs through their role in removing toxins and excess nutrients from the body in the form of gas. The possible role of the liver in dumping excess potassium into the intestines and having them removed from the body in the form of gas would make the function of the kidneys easier in dealing with excess potassium. Note that although the liver is able to neutralize some toxins and wastes, it is not supposed to neutralize essential nutrients, so excess essential nutrients may have to be removed from the body in the form of gas.

Long-term effects of blood flow on nerves and neurons

The brain, hands and feet are the three endpoints of the body to which blood reaches via arteries before returning to the heart via veins. (The liver is an internal organ to which blood reaches before returning to the heart.) Thus, blood waves constantly crash on the brain, hands and feet with force and heat. Over time, this will damage the blood-nerve barriers in the hands and feet and the blood-brain barriers in the brain, leading to nerve

and neuron diseases, as blood is toxic to neurons and nerves. Below I describe one of my personal experiences with blood flow in support of this hypothesis.

I have practiced qigong and meditation for more than 40 years. During qigong and meditation, blood flow to the palms of my hands is increased; I can feel the pressure of blood pushing against my palms, and the temperature of my palms can be increased from resting levels by $0.7^{\circ}F$.

In late April 2022, I found that my left ring finger hurt when it was quickly bent. I also noticed that tremor occurred in the finger when I looked at it and held it steady or moved it slowly. Once I realized I might have a nerve problem in my left ring finger, I tried to fix this problem with qigong, as I had done before for other health problems. I knew that thinking of the hands during qigong would increase blood flow into the hands, and I reasoned that increased blood flow would bring more nutrients to the hands and fingers, so I put my mind on the hand and finger constantly during my qigong practices. After an active qigong session, I also did a still qigong session (meditation) by holding my hands steady in an open position and thinking of them. Thinking of my left hand during qigong also caused tremor in the finger. When I put mind away from the finger, the tremor went away.

In March 2023, I realized that the tremor in the finger might be caused by the increased blood flow. An explanation for this is that over time, increased blood flow into the left hand during daily qigong practices wore out the blood-nerve barrier in the finger and toxins in the blood damaged nerves in the finger. Up to this point, I always practiced qigong with the open hands. Having found a possible cause for the tremor, I started practicing qigong with the hands opened slowly, then loosely closed slowly, then held loosely closed a little longer during the slow-flowing movements of the arms and other body parts. This repeated opening and closing of the hands control the amount of blood flow into the fingers, where the open hands let more blood flow into the fingers and the closed hands let less blood flow into the fingers. Before long, I found that my left finger no longer hurt when I bent it quickly and that the tremor disappeared completely. Now, whenever my mind is placed on my left hand, I practice the three-part sequence with the hand repeatedly to control blood flow into the finger. This experience illustrates the power of the mind on the direction and intensity of the blood flow in the body. Even in the state of relaxation when the heart beats slower, the mind could lead to intense blood flow into the finger. Over time, this could damage the blood-nerve barrier in the finger. The above experience led me to reason the effect of stress on the health of the brain. During stress in which the heart beats faster, the blood flows

more intensely toward the brain than toward the hands and feet. Over time, this could damage the blood-brain barriers in the brain and cause neurological disorders. Stress also disrupts the process of removing toxins from the neurons and the body, leading to more neurological and other disorders. The relaxation response is associated with reduced blood flow to the brain, which is less hard on the blood-brain barriers than the stress response.

Discussion

Traditional Chinese medicine principles state that qigong promotes a healthy flow of qi in the body. However, qi is an unverified concept (Lee et al. 2008). In this study, I explored the effect of qigong on blood flow in the body. Qigong induces the relaxation response that increases blood flow to the hands above resting levels, but reduces blood flow to the brain (the frontal lobe) slightly below resting levels. This blood flow pattern is called the relaxation flow. Over time, the level of brain blood flow elicited by qigong is less difficult on brain blood vessels than increased blood flow above resting levels during stress. In the long term, qigong keeps brain blood vessels in better shape than stress. So the relaxation response enables the brain to maintain its ability to have increased blood flow for a longer term than the stress response. Daily qigong practice strengthens the neurovascular association that enables the rapid elicitation of the relaxation flow by gentle body movements along with the mind gently set on the palms.

Stress increases blood flow to the brain above resting levels, while the relaxation response elicited by qigong reduces blood flow to the brain below or towards resting levels. Increased blood flow to the brain followed by reduced blood flow to the brain is helpful in cleaning neurons (Fultz et al. 2019). Besides qigong, sauna and cold shower can have similar effects on brain blood flow. Exercise is known to increase blood flow to the brain. However, after doing exercise, my forehead temperature measurements were below its resting range, suggesting reduced blood flow to the brain below resting levels. My cool forehead after exercise resulted from the sweating on the forehead (Sato et al. 2011) followed by reduced blood flow to the frontal lobe (Sato et al. 2011), in a similar way as clammy palms result from reduced blood flow to the hands (Crandall et al. 2005). Moreover, I found that performing push-ups, which involve rapid and strenuous muscle movements, leads to reduced hand and brain blood flow below resting levels. On the other hand, performing qigong, which involves slow and gentle muscle movements, leads to increased hand blood flow above resting levels. To emphasize the importance of relaxation to the health of neu-

rons and nerves, I propose that the phrase “use it or lose it” be revised as “use and relax it or lose it”.

Increased blood flow to the hands induced during qigong could lead to injuries to nerves in the fingers over time. It is important to be aware of this possibility and make proper adjustments to the form of the fingers during qigong. Similarly, increased blood flow to the brain during stress could lead to injuries to neurons in the brain over time.

This study has demonstrated that it is possible to monitor changes in blood flow pattern at home by taking palm and forehead temperature measurements. How much relaxation should a person incorporate into his or her lifestyle? I propose that a guideline for addressing this question be based on its effect on the amount of gas the person’s body passes during the day because passing gas is an effective way of removing toxins, neuronal wastes and excess nutrients from the body. If these substances were allowed to stay in the colon for many hours, then they would be reabsorbed back into the blood and into the neurons again. Enough relaxation should be incorporated into a person’s lifestyle so that the number of times the person passes gas during the day is not significantly reduced by the stress response.

Additional Information and Declarations

Competing Interests

The author is interested in exploring the potential of the insights in medical applications. No content on this paper should ever be used as a substitute for direct medical advice from your doctor or other qualified clinician.

Author Contributions

Xiaoqiu Huang conceived and designed the experiments, performed the experiments, analyzed the data, wrote and edited the paper.

Data Availability

Eight files of data in plain text along with a README file are provided in a single ZIP file in Supplementary Information.

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